

Influence of Political Skill and Servant Leadership Toward Career Satisfaction in PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk – Surabaya Branch Office

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Abstract: This research aimed to explain and analyze the influence of political skill and servant leadership on career satisfaction among employees PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk – Surabaya Branch Office. This study used quantitative methods to obtain data taken from the result of an online questionnaire for employees, with a response rate of 57%. The populations of this study were employees of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk - Surabaya Branch Office. The sampling technique used was saturated sampling method on 40 organic employees. The data analysis used in this research was Partial Square (PLS) by using smartPLS 3.0 software. The research showed that political skill has no effect on career satisfaction. The further results revealed that servant leadership has a significant positive effect on career satisfaction. The findings of this study provided banking company managers with a way to identify the constructs that best in explaining servant leadership, especially during these times of the Covid-19 pandemic. All employees needed to improve the quality of the agenda that was held outside working hours that aimed to strengthen relations between employees such as seminars, arisan, and gatherings that could train communication to improve political skill. In addition, the company was advised to increase career satisfaction surveys so the level of employee satisfaction with their careers could be known so that employees remain loyal to the company.

Keywords: Political Skill, Servant Leadership, Career Satisfaction

1. Introduction

PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk won five award categories in the 2017 Indonesia Banking Award (IBA) contest; this was written in the company's achievement report. By receiving this award, the company's optimism in achieving corporate targets at the end of the year increased and it can continue the positive performance record. PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk has formed various strategies and steps to encourage optimism in the company. The award shows the company's performance that has received recognition from the public. The performance that has been created by PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) will be maintained. In addition, Good Corporate Governance (GCG) will continue to be implemented will continue to increase solidarity with the leadership of the

head office, branch offices, and regional offices of PT. Tabungan Negara (Persero) (Nisaputra, 2017).

PT Bank Tabungan Negara, (Persero), Tbk (Bank BTN) is a State-Owned Enterprise (BUMN) engaged in banking. Bank BTN is committed to being a bank that serves and supports the housing sector financing through three main products, individual banking, business, and sharia (Bank BTN, 2019). The main task of the financial services sector (banking) is to increase the growth of the national micro and macroeconomic potential with one of its roles, namely obtaining optimal profits to improve the small and medium credit business sectors (MSMEs). Providing banking services and collecting and distributing funds are the main activities of financial sector services (Bank Indonesia, 2013).

The purpose of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk to advance the company, namely, to compete with other conventional banking sectors, potential resources need to be utilized properly. Therefore, for the sake of increasing company performance, employees always try to provide knowledge and skills. Because employees who have skills and are reliable and have skills, in the long run, can make the company have a good development in its human resources (Nikoloski, 2016).

A person's career in an organization is largely determined by how the policies and commitment of the organization to its employees. Therefore, organizations must assist their employees in planning and developing employee careers so that employees can achieve career satisfaction which will have an impact on employee loyalty to the organization or company. However, in reality, not all companies can assist in employee career planning so that there are still employees who are dissatisfied with their careers. JobStreet.com (2020) surveyed 17,623 correspondents regarding employee satisfaction with their work. The survey results showed 73% of employees were dissatisfied with their work. The following are the factors that cause employees to feel dissatisfied with their work. Through the application of potential human capital, it will create the success of a good organization going forward. The application is by using political skills possessed by employees so that it can improve the performance of an organization or company (Vigoda-Gadot et al., 2016). People who are working in a company must be able to do something skillfully and always implement it in his/her work environment, this is a requirement that must be owned by employees. This is to get career satisfaction in the future for personal and corporate interests. Therefore, it is necessary to know a political skill that is demanded by companies in all aspects that lead to the workforce, human resources, and knowledge that is in the company and are needed to work for advancement in the career ladder. Political skill is needed to make employees effective in the company; this has long been used as a competency (Game, 2016). Political skill is shown as a predictor of the performance achievements of employees as well as strong work results. In essence, every employee is free to determine their respective satisfaction and how much success they have and determine the desired career. However, every employee must be competent and have more insight into broad knowledge in his career to developing personal and creative potential, because currently there is intense competition in the world of work. (Treadway et al., 2013).

Career satisfaction points to the feelings of an individual's toward the achievement of career goals and satisfaction, in a study conducted by Latif, Machuca, Marimon, &

Sahibzada (2020) argues that servant leadership will enhance employees' career satisfaction. Servant leaders aid subordinates to grow and succeed by showing genuine interest in their career development and providing subordinates the opportunities to improve their skills, this encouragement of leadership can affect subordinates' career satisfaction (Latif et al., 2020). Servant Leadership emphasizes employee's development and growth within a context of moral and social concern (Latif et al., 2020). Servant leaders empower the followers, support and encourage them, and facilitate their growth and development (Latif et al., 2020).

Based on pre-research interviews with the branch coordinator of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk - Surabaya branch office said that the leadership style of servant leadership has been applied in the organization. An example is a leader who has shown concern for employees and pushed employees towards a better direction in increasing competitive advantage through the innovative development of digital-based products, services, and strategic banking networks. In addition, the application of servant leadership style at PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk - Surabaya branch office, which is implemented through building cooperation in synergy with all stakeholders based on a visionary, sincere, open, and empowering attitude in a productive "teamwork" by upholding mutual trust and respect. employee input for the progress of the company and also have an impact on the achievement of employee career satisfaction. In this case, visionaries, competent in their fields, always develop themselves with the latest technology so that leaders can guide and empower employees to work optimally. In this case, political skills according to the branch coordinator can get the job done and achieve well. In addition, the ranks of leaders who have the nature of serving sincerely to employees or subordinates will be very influential to build good relationships with coworkers is very important because employees are required to work as a team. Political skills are the basis for building a sense of comfort and communication so that work is done quickly and can achieve targets and career satisfaction. So this study aims to analyze the effect of political skills and servant leadership on career satisfaction.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Political Skill

Political skill is the ability to interpret the behavior of other people in an organizational environment and build relationships with that person so that it can influence and be used to achieve goals both organizationally and personally (Gunaedi & Kistyanto, 2018). Campbell & Phillip (2013) describe political skill as the ability to build relationships (networking) maximally to achieve organization, team, and individual goals. In facing job challenges, leaders need to understand, motivate, and influence others to determine a clear direction and vision, align resources to get work done and build employee commitment and engagement. Political skill is a skill to understand other people by using knowledge to influence people in their work environment using various ways to achieve the goals of the company's vision and mission and increase personal interests (Ferris et al., 2005).

In theoretical terms, someone who has political skill who is in the appropriate situation, and constituents can have an understanding of how to interact socially and be more adaptable to the company and its organizational culture. Attitudes and responses

possessed by employees can be influenced by the building of trust from the network they have, namely by a collection of social competencies that support, build, and complement each other (Vigoda-Gadot et al., 2016). One form of social skill or potential that a company has is political skill. A person who has political skill can ensure and position himself correctly according to the situation and have influenced by using an effective way that is seen as the application of sincere actions (Treadway et al., 2013). The conclusion that can be drawn from some of the above theories is (political skill) is the use of knowledge in all things and can understand and influence other people to achieve personal and organizational goals in the workplace and organizational environment.

2.2 Servant Leadership

Servant leadership is leadership that has an ethical and serving concept, introduced in 1970 by Spears (1996) in his book entitled "Character and Servant Leadership: Ten Characteristics of Effective, Caring Leaders" which contains the theory that servant leadership arises from sincere feelings. thus creating a leadership role in serving employees and providing guidance, which emerges from the heart of each individual to serve sincerely. Sendjaya & Sarros (2002) explains that servant leadership is a leader with the nature of prioritizing the interests of others, the needs of others above themselves, and visionary. A commitment to serving others is what servant leadership has.

Vondey (2010) explains that servant leadership is the characteristic of a leader who cares about the dynamics and growth of the lives of employees, subordinates, and their communities within a company or organization so that he is more concerned with these things rather than prioritizing his/her preferences and personal ambitions to be achieved (personal ambitions). According to Stone et al., (2004) servant leadership is a leader who focuses on his/her employees by serving sincerely, where these employees are in peripheral organizational problems and get the main attention. Serving leaders are a series of virtues, which are characterized by having good qualities and good moral qualities as well as moral excellence in a person or in general. From some of the theories and opinions above, it can be concluded that "servant leadership" is a leader who is humble and serves sincerely, and cares for the lives of his employees or subordinates and the community within his company or organization.

2.3 Career Satisfaction

Career satisfaction is defined as a pleasant or positive emotional state when it results from one's assessment and work experience (Greenhaus et al., 1990). Martínez-León et al., (2018) explain that career satisfaction is a career achievement in the perception of an individual and prospects for sustainability for advancement in his career path. On the other hand, career satisfaction is referred to as career achievement with individual assessments related to subjective career success (Sultana et al., 2016).

Career satisfaction is a real achievement or that is felt and accumulated by individuals as a result of their work experience (Blickle et al, 2010). Meanwhile, Abdullah (2017) defines that regardless of an outside perspective, every individual can experience his success directly, this is known as subjective career success (career satisfaction). Where employees and each individual are expected to be able to manage their career paths rather than always

depending on the direction of the company or organization. From several definitions described, it can be concluded that career satisfaction is the satisfaction felt by individuals which refers to what has been obtained in their career achievements such as position, power, and salary. Tukijan & Winarti (2014) suggest that individual career satisfaction is influenced by several factors, including the attitude of the boss, education, experience, one's fate.

2.4 Political Skill and Career Satisfaction

Political skill the concept of political skill emanates from the work of Game (2016), who suggested that organizations are political and for one to be successful, certain social skills are vitally important. Drawing on these works, Ferris and colleagues specified a political skill construct, which measured “the ability to effectively understand others at work and to use such knowledge to influence others to act in ways that enhance one’s personal and/or organizational objectives (Ferris et al., 2005). In terms of how people acquire these skills, there are certain aspects of political skill that can be more dispositional (such as interpersonal influence), but there are other dimensions (networking ability) that can be developed and learned and that enable an individual to better cope with his or her work environment (Ferris et al., 2005). Social influence theory Todd, Harris, Harris, & Wheeler (2009) lead researchers to believe that those individuals who are politically skilled are better able to influence others to achieve desired outcomes and goals than are those who are not politically skilled. Social influence theory suggests that individuals strive to develop and preserve meaningful social relationships (Todd et al., 2009). Further, individuals who are better at maintaining high-quality workplace relationships are more likely to be satisfied with their careers and lives in general. Political skill is a variable that will aid employees in developing and preserving relationships. Those employees who are politically skilled can influence others, appear to be sincere, conduct themselves in socially astute ways, and better develop networks Ferris et al., (2005), all of which are important in developing social relationships and which ultimately are related to higher career and life satisfaction. In this sense, we would suggest that an employee who perceives a less than optimal career satisfaction (or life satisfaction) might seek to incorporate political skills, such as influencing others at work and establishing larger networks, to change their assessment of the outcome. In this scenario, they would be actively seeking to balance the ratio of control desired over control possessed. Thus we predicted the following:

H1. Political skills are positively related to career satisfaction

2.5 Servant Leadership and Career Satisfaction

Career satisfaction refers to the individual's feelings towards achieving career goals and satisfaction (Latif & Marimon, 2019). The main premise of this theory is that servant leadership behavior contributes to the development and maintenance of strong interpersonal relationships between leaders and employees and plays an important role in helping employees reach their full potential (Latif & Marimon, 2019). Servant leadership emphasizes employee development and growth in the context of moral and social care (Latif & Marimon, 2019). Serving leaders help employees to grow and succeed by showing a genuine interest in career development and providing opportunities for employees to improve their skills and career satisfaction (Latif et al., 2020). Chiniara & Bentein (2016) in their research found that servant leadership has a significant influence on employee

competency needs. Chughtai (2019) in his study found a significant effect of servant leadership on career planning. Based on these arguments it is hypothesized:

H2: Servant leadership is positively related to career satisfaction

Figure 1.
Conceptual Framework

3. Research Method

By considering the nature of the research problem, the present study employed a quantitative approach. The reason is that the research aims to test a set of hypotheses include confirming and adding to the present theory. Data have been collected from a representative sample of the population, the next step is to analyze them to answer our research questions. Subsequently, general guidelines are provided for calculating and displaying basic descriptive statistics (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016: 271).

This research uses the technique non-probability sampling, with type purposive sampling, approach through judgment sampling. Judgment sampling involves the choice of subjects who are most advantageously placed or in the best position to provide the information required (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016: 248). Sekaran & Bougie (2016: 264) proposes the following rules of thumb for determining sample size: sample sizes larger than 30 and less than 500 are appropriate for most research (Kistyanto et al., 2021). The population of this research is the permanent employees of PT. State Savings Bank (Persero) Tbk. The number of samples in this study was 40 employees. Data collection through online and offline interviews, polls, and online-based questionnaires was conducted by researchers.

In measuring the political skill, it is using 4-indicators from Ferris et al., (2005) which consist of social intelligence, interpersonal influence, networking skill, and real sincerity. 5-Indicators for measuring servant leadership was developed by Dennis & Bocarnea (2005) namely compassion, empowerment, vision, humility, and trust. Finally, in measuring the career satisfaction variable using 5-indicators from Greenhaus et al., (1990) which consist of career achievement, career success, income, goal progress, and skill development. Data analysis uses an approach Structural Equation Model (SEM) method by Partial Least Square (PLS) supported by program computer software Smart-PLS 3.0, and SPSS 23.0 for the analysis demographic statistics of respondent characteristics and variables descriptive analysis. All items were rated on a 5-point Likert scale, with respondents indicating their agreement or disagreement with each statement (1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree) (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016: 215).

By convention, for a well-fitting reflective model, path loadings should be above 0.70 (Henseler et al., 2012: 269). However, at the scale development research stage, loadings 0.50 to 0.60 are still acceptable (Ghozali & Latan, 2015: 37). In an adequate model, AVE should be greater than 0.50 (Chin, 1998; Höck & Ringle, 2006: 15). In a model adequate for exploratory purposes, composite reliabilities should be equal to or greater than 0.60 (Chin, 1998; Höck & Ringle, 2006: 15); equal to or greater than 0.70 for an adequate model for confirmatory purposes (Henseler et al., 2012: 269); and equal to or greater than 0.80 is considered good for confirmatory research (Daskalakis & Mantas, 2008: 288). By convention, the same cutoffs apply: greater or equal to 0.80 for a good scale, 0.70 for an acceptable scale, and 0.60 for a scale for exploratory purposes (Garson, 2016: 64). Level significance: P-value < 0.05 or level significance T-value > 1.96 (Garson, 2016: 97).

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Convergent Validity

The results of all indicators can be said to be valid if it has an outer loading value above 0.70. However, the outer loading of 0.50 to 0.60 is acceptable as long as the model is still in the development stage (Ghozali, 2014). This study uses an outer loading value threshold of 0.50.

Figure 2. Test Measurement Model
 Source: Smart-PLS 3.0

Table 1.
 Loading Factor of Each Indicator

Variables	Indicator	Outer Loading	Explanation
Politic Skill	X.1.1	0.914	>0.50
	X.1.2	0.771	>0.50
	X.1.3	0.651	>0.50
	X.1.4	0.748	>0.50
Seroant Leadership	X.2.1	0.792	>0.50
	X.2.2	0.786	>0.50

	X.2.3	0.792	>0.50
	X.2.4	0.870	>0.50
	X.2.5	0.740	>0.50
Career	Y.1.1	0.727	>0.50
Satisfaction	Y.1.2	0.876	>0.50
	Y.1.3	0.717	>0.50
	Y.1.4	0.742	>0.50
	Y.1.5	0.739	>0.50

Source: Compiled by Author

The outer model in this study consists of variables of political skill, servant leadership, and career satisfaction, which are described by each indicator. The results of the convergent validity test are presented in table 1. In table 1, all variables have a value of more than 0.50. So it can be concluded that the indicators of this research variable have a good convergent validity value.

4.2 Composite Reliability

The validity and reliability of each variable can be seen from the composite reliability value of a construct for each variable. From the constructed value, it can be said to have high reliability if it has a constructed value above 0.70. Table 2 shows the reliability value of each construct.

Table 2
Composite Reliability Value

Variables	<i>Composite Reliability</i>	Explanation
Politic Skill	0.848	Reliable
<i>Servant Leadership</i>	0.852	Reliable
Career Satisfaction	0.863	Reliable

Source: Compiled by Author

Based on table 2 it can be interpreted that the political skill variable has a value of 0.848, which is higher than 0.70 so that this construct has high reliability. The servant leadership variable has a composite reliability value of 0.852 that is classified as having a high-reliability value because it has a value above 0.70. The career satisfaction variable has a value of 0.863, which means that this variable has a high reliability value because it has a value above 0.70. So it can be concluded that all variables in the construct are considered to have good composite reliability.

4.3 Cronbach's alpha

Cronbach's alpha can strengthen the results of previous reliability tests. If the previous composite reliability value has a good value, then Cronbach's alpha value will consistently follow it. The following is a table of values of Cronbach's alpha.

Table 3
Cronbach's Alpha Value

Variables	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	Explanation
Politic Skill	0.806	Reliable
<i>Servant Leadership</i>	0.765	Reliable
Career Satisfaction	0.775	Reliable

Source: Compiled by Author

The Cronbach's alpha value is considered reliable if it has a value of more than 0.70. Based on table 3, it can be seen that of all the constructs, Cronbach's alpha value is good, so it is considered reliable.

4.4 Analysis R-Square

Table 4.
R-Square Value

Variable	R-Square
Politic Skill	-
Servant Leadership	-
Career Satisfaction	0,340

Source: Compiled by Author

In the R-Square value above, the model of the influence of political skill and servant leadership on career satisfaction shows the amount of 0.340 from the R-Square value. So it can be interpreted that the political skill and servant leadership variables can explain the construct variables of career satisfaction by 34%, while the other 0.660 or 66% are explained by variables outside this research.

4.5 Prediction Relevance Test

The partial least square model can be determined by looking at the predictive relevance Q-square value. Below is the predictive relevance Q-square value in this research model:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= 1 - (\sqrt{1 - R^2}) \\
 &= 1 - (\sqrt{1 - 0.3402}) \\
 &= 0.099
 \end{aligned}$$

The calculated predictive relevance test obtained a value of 0.099 from the Q-square predictive relevance so that the value was greater than zero. From this, it shows that the model of this study has a predictive relevance of 9.9%.

4.6 Causality Test

Testing of the inner model is carried out to determine the relationship between variables and the significant value of the research model in the path coefficients table as presented in table 5 as follows:

Table 5
Path Coefficients Results

Relationship Between Variables	Original Sample	T-Statistics	Explanation	Conclusion
Politic Skill and Career Satisfaction	0,213	0,915	$\leq 1,96$ (Not Significant)	Hypothesis Rejected
Servant Leadership and Career Satisfaction	0,427	2,236	$\geq 1,96$ (Significant)	Hypothesis Accepted

Source: Compiled by Author

In table 5 above, the t-statistics value of political skill on career satisfaction is 0.915, which is < 1.96 . From this value, it is shown that the variable political skill does not affect

career satisfaction. The coefficient estimate is 0.213, it can be concluded that political skill does not affect career satisfaction even though the coefficient value possessed by political skill has a positive sign.

The t-statistics value of servant leadership on career satisfaction is 2,236, namely > 1.96 , and the coefficient estimate value is 0.427. This can be explained that servant leadership has a positive effect on career satisfaction.

4.7 The Effect of Political Skill on Career Satisfaction

From the results of this study, H1 was rejected because the resulting t-statistic value has a value of 0.915, which is less than 1.96, so it can be said that political skills do not affect career satisfaction. Political skills of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, Surabaya branch office does not affect career satisfaction. These results can be explained that although the political skills possessed by employees of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, Surabaya branch office is good or bad, it does not affect the increase or decrease in the career satisfaction of employees of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, Surabaya branch office. Through the results of interviews and observations with the branch coordinator which states that the relationship between the leader and employees is quite close and close, there is no gap even though there is a difference between the position of the leader and the employees under him, either at the office or during working hours or outside the office. still awake. However, it seems that the closeness or networking in this organization according to employees does not have an impact on employee career satisfaction. Interviews with the branch coordinator show that political skills do not have an impact / are less beneficial for both parties, namely leaders and subordinates so that it does not affect career satisfaction. Indicators of interpersonal and networking influence from political skills can be a weak indication of career satisfaction. Indicators of political skills are defined as social intelligence, interpersonal influence, networking skills, and real sincerity. The closeness of networking between leaders and employees and interpersonal influence does not seem to promise employee career satisfaction and maximum work results. As well as the lack of collaboration/teamwork and the mismatch of information between the consumer collection administration division and the collection/survey division in the field related to credit restructuring, when conducting direct surveys in the field seeing the belief that the debtor still has good business prospects or not, in this case, the employees the division still has a discrepancy between the information from the survey data and the restructuring process. This will later have an impact on employee career satisfaction and the achievement of banking targets for the CCRU (consumer collection remedial unit) billing division for debtors who are in arrears or problematic. So, the leaders and employees of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, the Surabaya branch office should focus more on the teamwork of employees and unit managers who see the long-term goals of the company towards achieving better targets and focus on achieving NPL (non-performing loans) and banking targets for services. better credit restructuring.

The same results in the research of Hayek et al., (2018) stated that political skill does not affect career satisfaction. The sample (N $\frac{1}{4}$ 856) was taken from large family-controlled financial services firm in Ecuador. Using Smart Partial Least Squares (PLS) structural equation modeling, our results showed that, in the unique Ecuadorian context, political skill

is more strongly related to career satisfaction than to performance evaluations or salary. In addition, the relationship between political skill and career satisfaction is partially mediated by affective commitment.

This result contradicts the research conducted by Breland et al., (2007) which explains that the career success of every employee or high individual will also tend to have a high level of political skill.

4.8 The Effect of Servant Leadership on Career Satisfaction

This study explains that servant leadership has a significant positive effect on career satisfaction. It can be seen from this that H2 is accepted because the t-statistics value shows a value of 2,236 which is more than 1.96. Several things, including the motivation that underlies every leader and employee to continue to develop and use a servant leadership style, where this style is considered an effort to achieve career success in a financial service company (banking), can cause some of these factors. The original sample value of servant leadership on career satisfaction is 0.427, it can be explained that the higher servant leadership at PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, Surabaya branch office, the higher the career satisfaction of employees of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk Surabaya branch office.

This result strengthens the research of Latif et al., (2020) which explains that servant leadership has a significant positive effect on career satisfaction in Spanish universities. The servant leadership variable has a high influence on the career satisfaction of employees of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, Surabaya branch office. One of the indicators of empowerment has the highest value so that employees are considered able to develop and empower skills and achievement of career satisfaction. An example is an indicator of the career success of employees who are encouraged by the leadership of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, a Surabaya branch office that is empowering and visionary in guiding so that in the future it can be more innovative and see the company's long-term goals towards achieving better targets and focus on achieving NPL (non-performing loans) to reduce credit risk non-performing loans as well as banking targets for better consumer credit services. The vision indicator emphasized by the leadership is that future employees can be more visionary and careful in solving work problems to increase career satisfaction at work. Servant leadership is considered to be a solution for the career satisfaction of employees of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, Surabaya branch office.

Through interviews with branch coordinators, servant leadership on "vision" (vision) is the idea of leaders and unit managers who see long-term goals, see an individual as someone active and worthy of respect, believes in the goals and future of each individual, and trying to serve individuals to achieve goals. Vision behavior at leader PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, the Surabaya branch office is considered to increase employee career satisfaction. The leadership's vision behavior is demonstrated by a guiding attitude in terms of achieving NPL (non-performing loans) individually as well as in banking units and targets, by believing in employees' abilities and paying attention to employees' interests. With this behavior, employees feel helped in achieving targets and achieving NPL (non-performing loans) and periodic briefing teams. In addition, it is

intended that PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, Surabaya branch office so that going better in the future in implementing good corporate governance.

This is indicated by Latif & Marimon (2019) which aim to validate the scale in measuring leadership serving leaders at the University. The second is to analyze how servant leadership affects career satisfaction and life satisfaction in academics. The total effect of serving leadership on career satisfaction is zero due to the competitive mediation of career satisfaction. The result of the direct effect is negative i.e. serving leadership causes a negative impact on career satisfaction.

5. Conclusion

In this study, political skill did not affect career satisfaction. This means that even if employees have a high or low political skill, this does not have an impact on employee career satisfaction at the Loan Administration division, Skip Tracer Coordinator, and Transaction Processing PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, Surabaya branch office.

Servant leadership has a significant and positive effect on career satisfaction. This means that the better the servant leadership style that the leaders of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, Surabaya branch office, this will have a positive impact on employee career satisfaction.

Suggestions for companies, from the research results, show that political skills do not affect career satisfaction. Leaders and employees of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, the Surabaya branch office should be able to focus more on teamwork in each division, especially the consumer collection administration division and the collection/survey division to improve communication more effectively and efficiently, such as clear objectives in open communication, build trust, create agendas/activities for team closeness, and the company creates a reward system so that team members/employees feel that their work is valued, by creating a reward system and unit managers who must look at the company's long-term goals towards achieving targets. better and focus on achieving NPLs (non-performing loans) to reduce the risk of bad credit and banking targets and for better credit restructuring services. For example, to intensify training to increase employee competence to increase employee knowledge at work to increase career satisfaction at work.

Based on the results of the servant leadership questionnaire that has been distributed to PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, Surabaya branch office, has empowerment indicators and statement items. It is employee empowerment with opportunities so that employees can develop skills, as well as career achievement and satisfaction, which has a value of 3.93 meaning very high value. The suggestions given by the researcher are the leaders of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, the Surabaya branch office must continue to strive to empower and serve employees and continue to apply a servant leadership style such as visionary behavior towards the organization. Vision behavior in the leadership of PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, Surabaya branch office is considered to increase employee career satisfaction. Guiding employees in terms of achieving NPL (non-performing loans) individually as well as units and employee targets in the case of bad credit can demonstrate the leadership's vision behavior. In that case, the role

of the serving leadership style in PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, the Surabaya branch office can be continuously improved to achieve higher career satisfaction.

This study has several limitations, including the sample, this is because PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, the Surabaya branch office began implementing split operations and social distancing by limiting operational activities at branch offices to avoid the transmission of the Covid -19 pandemic. This is done in anticipation of limiting the operating hours of the branch offices from 08.15-14.00 WIB, as well as limiting the number of employees who enter each day. Due to policies from the banking sector and government, researchers were only given a sampling limit of 40 organic employees at PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, Surabaya branch office. So that later for further research it is recommended to increase the number of samples and population to be studied so that the results obtained are more global.

Suggestions for the next researchers, in terms of the use of variables, in this study there is one variable that has no influence, namely the variable of political skill, for that based on the results of reviews and interviews, we suggest that further research consider using communication and innovative work behavior variables. We consider this to affect employee career satisfaction. In addition, in previous research, Rahman et al., (2020) the setting of innovative work behavior variables can become a mediating variable for each relationship between variables.

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